

IMPACT AND REFLECTION OF VISION AND MISSION STATEMENT ON CO-CURRICULAR ACTIVITIES OF SELECTED ENGLISH MEDIUM COLLEGES OF TEACHER EDUCATION

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INTRODUCTION

Co-curricular activities conducted in the educational institution are closely linked with the culture of the institution. Possibly, that is why they are the most remarkable feature of the institutions. The outlook towards it is most of the time building collaborative abilities, developing critical and creative thinking, problem solving attitude and reasoning etc. Vision and Mission statements of the institutions shoulder the responsibility as source of inspiration in crafting the various co-curricular activities.

RATIONALE FOR THE STUDY

Co-curricular activities play a prominent role in the overall development of the students. They also are instrumental in helping students explore their talents, abilities and thinking out of the box. Hence, they develop many attributes among the students like risk takers, innovators etc. Thus, the entire process of conducting co-curricular activities in a way impart education that leads to transform students into critical thinkers and investigators. The institution's vision and mission statement provides the strong foundation of values and ethics to work towards holistic development of students and creates a culture of working together for the betterment of the students.

STATEMENT OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Impact and Reflection of Vision and Mission Statement on Co-curricular Activities of Selected English Medium Colleges of Teacher Education

DEFINITIONS OF THE VARIABLES

IMPACT AND REFLECTION

For the present study impact and reflection has been defined as the perception of student teachers and teacher educators on the overall and specific behaviour of the selected colleges of teacher education

VISION STATEMENT

According to business dictionary, "An aspirational description of what an organization would like to achieve or accomplish in the mid-term or long-term future.

It is intended to serves as a clear guide for choosing current and future courses of action."

MISSION STATEMENT

According to business dictionary, "A written declaration of an organization's core purpose and focus that normally remains unchanged over time. Properly crafted mission statements (1) serve as filters to separate what is important from what is not, (2) clearly state which markets will be served and how, and (3) communicate a sense of intended

direction to the entire organization.”

VISION AND MISSION STATEMENT

For the present study vision and mission statement has been defined as the philosophy of the managements of selected English medium colleges of teacher education which projects where the institution should go and what major changes and challenges it should adopt and how to link its activities to the needs of the society and legitimize its existence

CO-CURRICULAR ACTIVITIES

For the present study co-curricular activities is defined as how the vision and mission statement has the impact and reflection on various activities other than the curricular activities. Co-curricular activities are not just a show off affair but various management functions are involved in the process and institutions conduct these activities with the intension of a commitment to life long learning through their vision and mission. Co-curricular activities

- a) Planning
- b) Execution
- c) Evaluation
- d) Reaching out

AIMS OF THE STUDY

The aims of the present study are:

1. To study the impact and reflection of the vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers and teacher educators in the area of co-curricular activities of selected colleges of teacher education in the area of Academic Excellence

Objectives of the study

1. To study the impact and reflection of the vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers and teacher educators in the area of co-curricular activities of selected colleges of teacher education affiliated to the University of Mumbai

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The present research study includes the impact and reflection of the vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers and teacher educators with respect to following areas.

- Co-Curricular Activities

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

For the present study only English Medium colleges of teacher education were selected within the geographical boundaries of greater Mumbai. Present study includes equal number of aided and unaided colleges of teacher education. While selecting the colleges of teacher education two criteria were kept in mind NAAC accredited and more than five years of existence. Hence only those colleges of teacher education were selected for the study.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The present study will highlight the need of crafting the vision and mission statement meaningfully. It will also create an awareness about how vision and mission statement are crucial in the holistic development of the students.

Also the significance of vision and mission statement in creating a reputation of the institution in this competitive world.

BRIEF THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE AREA

CO-CURRICULAR ACTIVITIES

A co-curricular activity is defined as a program or out-of-class activity, supervised and/or financed by the school, which provides curriculum-related learning and character-building experiences.¹

Co-curricular activities are not just a show off affair, it is a serious venture which should be conducted in various educational institutions with the intension that only participation is not right it is an honour and privilege to make a commitment to lifelong learning, good citizenship and a healthy lifestyle at all times. The basic purpose of conducting co-curricular activities is to provide students and teachers with the opportunity to develop to the maximum of their potential. The role of vision and mission statement is very vital when it comes to the manner in which these co-curricular activities are handled. The vision and mission statement of the various institutions helps immensely to create and develop sprit, commitment and connectedness through co-curricular activities. Thus, the philosophy of each institution incorporates its cultures, beliefs, value systems through their co-curricular activities.

Today when the educational institutions have begun to see their roles in terms of service to the society more seriously and have developed vision and mission statements that support their ideas. The issue is not to write but to then live the statements. When vision and mission statements are not lived up to, through various co-curricular activities then it will not enhance motivation.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The present research study aimed at impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on behaviour of student teachers and teacher educators of selected English medium colleges of teacher education. There were many areas and aspects which are compared. Hence the descriptive method of comparative type was adopted to compare the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour in the areas in the categories. A descriptive, comparative research design was used to compare the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the area of Co-curricular activities.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The population of present research study consists of student teachers and teacher educators of aided and unaided colleges of teacher education in the Greater Mumbai area.

SAMPLING

The B.Ed colleges of teacher education in Greater Mumbai are mainly of two types, aided and unaided. The researcher identified the colleges that are completed minimum 5 years of existence and atleast once gone through NAAC accreditation. The sample of the study was selected using purposive sampling method.

NATURE AND SIZE OF THE SAMPLE

¹ <http://deering.portlandschools.org/handbook/dhscocurricular.pdf> 20 May 2011

The sample of the present study consists of 570 student teachers studying in selected English medium aided and unaided colleges of teacher education affiliated to the University of Mumbai, situated in Greater Mumbai area, minimum 5 years of existence and atleast once gone through NAAC accreditation.

The sample of the present study also consists of 78 teacher educators teaching in selected English medium colleges of teacher education affiliated to the University of Mumbai, situated in Greater Mumbai area, minimum 5 years of existence and at least once gone through NAAC accreditation.

PREPARATION OF THE TOOLS

For the present research studies following tools were prepared by the researcher.

1. Personal data sheet for the student teachers.
2. Personal data sheet for the teacher educators.
3. Co-curricular activities Rating Scale

This rating scale was prepared by the researcher to study the opinion of the student teachers and teacher educators about the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on Co-curricular Activities. It is a five-point rating scale and contains 14 items.

DATA COLLECTION

Almost all the selected teacher education colleges cooperated and researcher got the permission to collect data.

ANALYSIS OF THE DATA

In this stage the tabulated data are scientifically and systematically studied in order to determine underlying, inherent facts or relationships.

Tabulation refers to the recording of the classified scores. The present study required the data collected from student teachers to be tabulated in the categories of type of institution of teacher education that is aided and unaided, gender wise composition of the student teachers and on the basis of qualifications.

The data collected from the teacher educators to be tabulated in the categories of type of institution of teacher education that is aided and unaided, qualification wise that is only M.Ed and M.Ed with Ph.D and /or M.Phil and on the basis of teaching experience from 0-12 years and 13 years and above.

In the present study, Descriptive Analysis was adopted

Figure 1.1

Descriptive statistics of scores of impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities of selected colleges of teacher education

Area	Categories	N	Mean	Median	Mode	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis
CCA	Total	570	57.54	59.00	66.00	8.79	-.761	.574
Type	Aided	330	58.39	60.00	66.00	9.14	-.875	.504
	Unaided	240	56.37	57.00	54.00	8.15	-.690	1.008
Gender	Male	47	55.46	55.00	54.00	8.08	-.228	0.40
	Female	523	57.73	59.00	66.00	8.83	-.813	.726
Quali	Grad	397	56.97	58.00	66.00	8.72	-.757	.704
	Post Grad	173	58.85	61.00	70.00	8.82	-.823	.415

The descriptive statistics for the Co-curricular Activities scores for student teachers of colleges of teacher education are presented in table 5.30. The mean and the median values for the total sample and for the categories do not differ much, which indicates normality of the distribution. The S.D. for all the distributions is almost the same. All the distributions are slightly negatively skewed showing high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on co-curricular activities in the total sample as well as in the categories. The kurtosis values indicate that the distributions are platykurtic in nature for all the categories. This indicates high concentration of scores at the higher end.

The original and the smoothed frequency polygons depict the distributions in a pictorial form and support the distribution of the description statistics.

Figure 1.2

Figure 1.2 The original and smoothed frequency polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities of colleges of teacher education almost align with each other with same rise and fall. The frequency polygon shows only one peak. The curve indicates that the distribution is platykurtic in nature, is negatively skewed and it does not have normal shape. It also shows that maximum distribution lies on the extreme end of the X axis which shows very high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities of selected colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.3

Figure 1.3 The original and smoothed frequency polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities of aided colleges of teacher education differs slightly from each other. The frequency polygon shows only one peak. The curve indicates that the distribution is platykurtic in nature, is negatively skewed and it does not have normal shape. It also shows that maximum distribution lies on the extreme end of the X axis which shows very high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities of selected aided colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.4

Figure 1.4 The original and smoothed frequency polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities of unaided colleges of teacher education differ from each other. The frequency polygon shows only one peak. The curves indicate that the distribution is platykurtic in nature, is negatively skewed and it does not have normal shape. It also shows that maximum

distribution lies on the extreme end of the X axis which shows very high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities of selected unaided colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.5

Figure 1.5 The original and smoothed frequency polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of male student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities of colleges of education differ from each other. The frequency polygon shows only one peak. The curve indicates that the distribution is platykurtic in nature, it is negatively skewed and it does not have normal shape. It also shows that maximum distribution lies at the center which does not show significant impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of male student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities of selected colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.6

Figure 1.6 The original and smoothed frequency polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of female student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities of colleges of teacher education almost aligns with each other with the same rise and fall. The frequency polygon shows only one peak. The curve indicates that the distribution is platykurtic in nature, it is negatively skewed and it does not have normal shape. It also shows that maximum distribution lies on the extreme end of the X axis which shows very high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of female student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities of colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.7

Figure 1.7 The original and smoothed frequency polygons for impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of graduate student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities of the colleges of teacher education almost align with each other and they also have the same rise and fall. The frequency polygon shows only one peak. The curve indicates that the distribution is platykurtic in nature, it is

negatively skewed and it does not have normal shape. It also shows that maximum distribution lies on the extreme end of the X axis which shows very high Impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of graduate student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities of selected colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.8

Figure 1.8 The original and smoothed frequency Polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of post graduate student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities of colleges of teacher education differs from each other. The frequency polygon shows only one peak. The curve indicates that the distribution is platykurtic in nature, it is negatively skewed and it does not have normal shape. It also shows that maximum distribution lies towards right indicating high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of post graduate student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities of selected colleges of teacher education.

Table 1.9

Descriptive statistics of scores of impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of co-curricular activities of selected colleges of teacher education

Area	Categories	N	Mean	Median	Mode	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis
CCA	Total	78	51.48	52.00	65.00	11.45	-.790	0.58
Types	Aided	44	51.11	52.00	65.00	11.17	-.763	.147
	Unaided	34	51.97	52.50	65.00	11.94	-.869	.013
Quali	M.Ed Ph.D and/or M.Phil	23	49.73	51.00	51.00	12.78	-1.056	.317
	M.Ed	55	52.21	52.00	65.00	10.88	-.591	0.64
Tg.Exp.	0-12yrs	50	56.96	58	70	11.95	-0.86	0.02
	13yrs&above	28	53.28	55.5	56	12.25	-0.81	0.34

The descriptive statistics for the Co-curricular Activities scores for teacher educators of colleges of teacher education are presented in table 5.32. The mean and the median values for the total sample and for the categories do not differ much, except for the teacher educators with teaching experience 0-12 years, which indicates normality of the distribution. The S.D. for all the distributions is almost the same. All the distributions are slightly negatively skewed showing high co-curricular Activities in the total sample as well as the categories. The kurtosis values indicate that the distributions for the aided and unaided colleges of education and teacher educators with teaching experience between 0-12 years are leptokurtic or peaked in nature and the distributions for the total sample, teacher educators with qualification Ph.D, M.Phill, M.Ed and teacher educators with teaching experience 13 years and above are platykurtic in nature . This indicates high concentration of scores at the higher end.

The original and the smoothed frequency polygons depict the distributions in a pictorial form and support the distribution of the descriptive statistics

Figure 1.10

Figure 1.10 The original and smoothed frequency Polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of co-curricular activities of colleges of teacher education differ significantly. The frequency polygon shows two peaks. The distribution is negatively skewed and the curve is platykurtic in nature. It indicates maximum distribution lies towards right showing high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of co-curricular activities of selected colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.11

Figure 1.11The original and smoothed frequency Polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of co-curricular activities of aided colleges of teacher education differs significantly. The frequency polygon shows two peaks. The distribution is negatively skewed and the curve is leptokurtic. It indicates maximum distribution lies towards right showing high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of co-curricular activities of selected aided colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.12

Figure 1.12 The original and smoothed frequency polygons for the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of co-curricular activities of unaided colleges of teacher education differ from each other. The frequency polygon shows very different flat peak. The distribution is negatively skewed and the curve is leptokurtic. It indicates maximum distribution in the middle showing not very high impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of co-curricular activities of selected unaided colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.13

The following diagram displays the percentage of impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of co-curricular activities in the category of qualifications of selected colleges of teacher education.

Figure 1.13 From the bar diagram it is seen that the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of co-curricular activities in the category of qualifications of selected colleges of teacher education M.Ed with Ph.D, and/or M.Phil teacher educators is lesser than that of teacher educators with only M.Ed qualifications.

Figure 1.14

The following diagram displays the percentage of impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of co-curricular activities in the category of teaching experience of selected colleges of teacher education

Figure 1.14 From the bar diagram it is seen that the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of co-curricular activities in the category of teaching experience of selected colleges of teacher education teacher educators with 0-12 years teaching experience is greater than that of teacher educators with teaching experience 13 years and above.

Major Findings

The impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities does not differ significantly in the gender category. It is seen that the impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of student teachers in the area of co-curricular activities is significantly different in the categories type of institutions and qualifications. The greater impact and reflection of vision and mission statement being in aided colleges of teacher education and post graduate student teachers.

The impact and reflection of vision and mission statement on the specific behaviour of teacher educators in the area of co-curricular activities does not differ significantly in the categories of type of institutions, qualifications and teaching experience.

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